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Teacher Qualifications and Academic Performance of Pupils in Public Primary Schools in Hargeisa District

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Abstract

This study investigated effect of teacher qualifications on the academic performance of pupils in primary schools in Hargeisa districts. Teacher qualifications were operationalized as Formal education, certification and teaching experience. The study emerged from the deteriorating academic achievement of pupils in Somaliland National Primary Examinations. The deteriorating academic performance was well demonstrated from increase number of failures in Somaliland National Exams. The study employed cross sectional survey research design, on a sample of 160 teachers, the study found out that, $F_o = 15.838 > F(2,157) = 3.06$; $p = .000$. The eta-square returned an average value of $\eta^2 = 16.8\%$. Therefore, teacher qualification accounts for 16.8% of the variance in academic performance of pupils in public primary schools in Hargeisa. The rest 83.2% are due to factors not investigated here, and errors in measurements. The study findings indicate that teacher qualifications affect to the academic performance of pupils in public primary schools in Hargeisa District.

Keywords: Teacher Qualification, Academic Performance, High Qualifications, Moderate Qualification, Low Qualification, Licensure and Certification

1. INTRODUCTION

Teachers' qualification is a particular skill or type of experience or knowledge someone possesses to make him or her suitable to teach (Zuzovsky, 2009). But Hammond and Anderson (1991) define teacher qualifications as the credentials and general intellectual skills a teacher holds. Further, teacher qualifications have been defined as holding at least bachelor degree from an accredited university, solid teaching experience and licensure (Learn How to Become, 2019). More so, teacher qualification is a pertinent skill and licensure; a standard certificate in a state-approved teacher education program (Jacob, 2014). All these definitions concur that teacher qualifications reflect teachers' formal education, experience and licensure and certification. Teacher qualification plays a pertinent role in boosting the academic performance of students. Literally, teacher qualifications can be measured from two perspectives: formal education and licensure (Jacob, 2015). This paper will explore teacher qualifications in terms formal education, teaching experience and certification.

Teacher qualifications have been linked to academic performance. A study conducted by Zuzovsky(2003) with a sample size 371 mathematics teachers and 317 science teachers who taught about 4,000 students in 149 sampled

classes, each in every one of the sampled schools investigated the effect of teacher qualifications on the academic performance of students. The study adopted quasi-experimental design. The study found out that there was a positive relationship between teacher qualifications and academic performance. Other studies that showed positive correlation between teacher qualifications and student performance include: (Betts, Zau, & Rice, 2003; Ferguson & Ladd, 1996; Wayne & Youngs, 2003).

More so, another study on the impact of teacher qualifications on the academic performance of students was carried out by Rice (2003) over teachers holding different certificates were assigned to teach mathematics and science to students. The study revealed that teachers who earned advanced degrees had a positive impact on high school mathematics and science achievement. Additionally, a recent global study by Emery (2012) investigated the effect primary English teachers' qualifications on academic performance of the English proficiency of students. Data were collected via the use of an electronic survey, which gathered almost 2,500 responses and in-depth face-to-face interviews with classroom teachers and head teachers in nine countries around the world. Subjects represented rural and urban teachers who worked in state and private institutions. The findings indicate that teachers with high qualifications had strong positive effect on the academic performance of students. Furthermore, a study conducted by Collier (2013) explored the relationship between teacher qualifications and academic performance of students. The study adopted Longitudinal Panel Survey. Data was collected from a sample of 19000 students tested on their scores of mathematics and reading. Questionnaire was administered to parents, students and teachers. The study found out that teachers with higher level of qualifications had strong positive influence on the performance of students over mathematics and reading scores than their counterparts.

Most of the studies published on Somaliland education concentrated on reviews, policy analysis, teacher features, student characteristics, and some others in the field of research papers. Therefore, this paper explores the impact of teacher qualifications on the performance of pupils in the district of Hargeisa public primary schools.

Moreover, in the last five years, the academic performance of pupils in public primary schools has declined-the number of pupils did rise by 21 percent between 2014-2018. In Somaliland, the number of failures was 31% in 2014 and 30% in 2015, 40 percent in 2016, 51.2% in 2017 and 48.4% in 2018. Between 2014 and 2018, the number of failures increased by 16 percent in Hargeisa. The proportion of failures was 36% in 2014, 38% in 2015, 40% in 2016, 52.2% in 2017 and 51.97% in 2018.

On average, the performance of pupils in primary schools in Hargeisa dropped 16% in the last five years, delineating an average rise of percentage fail of 3.2% each year. In spite of the poor performance of primary school education, the effect of teacher qualifications on academic performance has not been investigated.

Therefore, this paper attempts to explore if teacher qualifications have any involvement of the deteriorating academic performance of students in public primary schools in Hargeisa District as reflected in National Exams Office (2018).

Consequently, the findings of this research are expected to help the Ministry of Education improve the education system of Somaliland.

2. METHODS

The target population was 675 teachers from 45 public primary schools in Hargeisa District (Ministry of Education and Science, 2018). The accessible population was 330 teachers from 21 primary schools in Hargeisa District. 21 schools can be reached by the researcher, within the allocated time and resources. The sample size consisted of 178 teachers. Krejcie and Morgan (1970) recommend that a population of 330 will use 178, at level of confidence 95%, and 5% margin error. The study used structured questionnaire which enabled the researcher to collect data on teacher qualifications within a short period of time. Documents to be examined including the first term examination. One Way ANOVA was also used to assess if there were significant differences between the means of the groups of teacher qualifications.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Employment Status of the Respondent

Respondents were requested to state their employment status. Employment status was deemed important to the study because the teacher's engagement could determine the pupils' performance. Therefore, Figure 4 depicts the employment status of the teachers.

Figure 1: Employment status of the respondents.

Figure 1 depicts the employment status of the respondents. It shows that 65.4% of the teachers of public primary schools in Hargeisa are full-time teachers while 30.6% work as part time. As a result, there are more full-time teachers in public primary schools in Hargeisa than part time teachers.

3.2. Professional Training of the Respondents

Respondents were requested to show their professional training. Professional training was necessary to the study as a sign of how the performances of particular teachers are. The results are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Professional training of the respondents.

Figure 2 portrays that majority (65.8%) of the teachers in public primary schools in Hargeisa District are teachers by profession while the minority (34.2%) have not undertaken professional training. This, therefore, means that as much as majority of the teachers in the public primary school in Hargeisa District, a number of them are not trained to teach and they affect students' performance.

The most important objective of this study was to determine effect of teacher qualifications on academic performance of pupils in primary schools in Hargeisa district. The teacher qualification was operationalized into formal education, teaching experience and certification. Respondents reacted several items on each variable and the responses were used to determine teacher qualification of the teachers in public primary schools as depicted in Table 5.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Teacher Qualifications and Academic Performance

Teacher Qualifications	Performance (%)	S	ϵ	N
Low	46	12.44	1.197	108
Moderate	58	14.84	2.23	44
High	61	21.48	7.59	8
Total	50.2	14.875	1.176	160

Note. N = Sample, S = Standard deviation, ϵ = standard error.

Table 1 shows the descriptive statistics of academic performance of pupils in primary schools in Hargeisa district against different teacher qualifications. It indicates that the average performance of students taught by high qualification teachers (61%, S = 21.48) was higher than the performance of the students taught by teacher with moderate qualifications (58%, S = 14.84) and the performance of pupils taught by low qualification teachers (46%, S = 12.44).

Nevertheless, performance of pupils having teachers with high teacher qualifications was higher than the performance of pupils taught by teachers with low and moderate teacher qualifications (61%, S = 21.48). This pointed out to the fact that academic performance of pupils increases with teachers' qualifications. However, results suggest that qualification of the teacher affects performance of students in public primary schools. Therefore, the better the teacher qualifications, the higher the academic performance of pupils in public primary schools in Hargeisa.

The hypothesis is that teacher qualification does not affect the academic performance of pupils in public primary schools in Hargeisa.

There is no significant difference in the average performance of students taught under teachers with Low, Moderate and High teacher qualifications.

$$H_{01}: TQF_L = TQF_M = TQF_H$$

$$H_{A1}: TQF_L \neq TQF_M \neq TQF_H$$

Where TQF_L is low teacher qualification; TQF_M is moderate teacher qualification and TQF_H stands for high teacher qualification.

The results for ANOVA are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: F-Statistics of Performance of Pupils with Teachers' Qualifications

Source of difference	Sums of Squares	Df	Mean square	P	F
Between	5906.098	2	2953.049	.000	15.838
Within	29273.502	157	186.455		
Total	35179.600	159			

Note. $F(2,157) = 3.06$

Table 2 presents the ANOVA statistics of the performance of pupils taught by teachers with low, moderate and high teacher qualifications. The results indicate that there is a significant difference in the performance of pupils taught by teachers with low, moderate and high qualifications, $F_0 = 15.838 > F(2,157) = 3.06$; $p = .000$. This led to the rejection of the null hypothesis. It shows that there is a significant difference in the performance of pupils taught by teachers with low, moderate and high qualifications. The study, therefore, established that teacher qualification affects academic performance of pupils in public primary schools in Hargeisa district. The more qualified the teacher, the higher the performance of the pupils.

The LSD Post-hoc produced a significant difference between the performance of students with low and moderate teacher qualifications, ($I-J = 12.400$, $P = .000$) and, these with low and high teacher qualifications ($I-J = 15.616$, $P = .002$). Therefore, teachers with low and moderate qualifications (58%, $S = 14.84$; 46%, $S = 12.44$) have lower performance than high qualification teachers (61%, $S = 21.48$). There is no difference between the moderate and high teacher qualifications.

The eta-square returned an average value of $\eta^2 = 16.8\%$. Therefore, teacher qualification accounts for 16.8% of the variance in academic performance of pupils in public primary schools in Hargeisa. The rest 83.2% are due to factors not investigated here, and errors in measurements. Academic performance can be affected by up to 16.8% through manipulation of teacher qualifications.

4. DISCUSSION

Foremost, the study established that teacher qualifications have a significant effect on the academic performance of pupils in public primary schools in Hargeisa, $F_0 = 15.838 > F(2,157) = 3.06$; $p = .000$). Hence, the formal education, experience and certification of the teacher have a significant effect on the performance. The finding that teacher qualifications affects student performance can be understood the fact that teachers with high qualifications are suitable to teach students. As Zuzovsky (2003) pointed out teacher qualification is a determinant factor that affects students' academic performance.

This finding compares with the study of Rice (2003) that found out that qualification of the teacher significantly affects the performance of pupils. Similarly, Hammond (2000) revealed that teacher qualification has a direct effect on the performance of students on different disciplines of learning. Moreover, teacher qualification of the teacher is indicated by the formal education, teaching experience and certification or licensure (Jacob, 2014). Consequently, teachers who meet these requirements tend to boost the academic performance of the pupils. This could mean that is a need to spend resources training teachers in advanced degrees. If teachers pursue advanced degrees in order to improve their skills and depth of knowledge, there is enough evidence, as this study has affirmed that advanced teacher education is associated with an improved student's performance. This finding is also supported by the point of view of UNESCO (1964) that teacher's inadequate preparation and experience during the training period is the cause of the poor academic performance of some pupils.

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